

Preparation and Infrared Studies of some *N*-Donor Complexes of *n*-Butyl-*n*-propyltin Dichloride

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Interest in the coordination chemistry of organotin halides is evident from recent publications¹. Here we report the preparation of the complexes of *n*-butyl-*n*-propyltin dichloride with some *N*-donors.

The results (Table 1) show that only triethylamine forms an equimolar complex even when present in excess while all the remaining bases form 1 : 2 (acid base) complexes.

Important ir spectral bands for *n*-butyl-*n*-propyltin dichloride and its complexes are given in Table 1. *N*-H deformations in case of piperidine, phenyl hydrazine and morpholine exhibits a red-shift on complexation² while for *o*- and *p*-toluidines they remain apparently unaffected. In case of tin-carbon stretching frequencies, which depend upon the effective nuclear charge on tin atom³, donation of electrons by nitrogen to tin is expected to shift them. The results show the same, though in some cases the shifts are insignificant⁴. In case of the complexes with *p*-toluidine, piperidine and *N*-ethylpiperidine appearance of only one Sn-C stretching band suggests a linear C-Sn-C arrangement^{3,5}, while in the remaining complexes the appearance of two bands suggests distortion from linearity⁶.

Sn-Cl stretching frequencies of organotin chlorides decrease with the increase in the number of alkyl groups attached to tin, and in case of diorganotin dichlorides^{7,8} they fall in the region 360-300 cm⁻¹. Donation of electrons by amines to tin atom decreases the positive charge on tin and would cause the lengthening of Sn-Cl bond leading to the decrease in its stretching frequencies^{8,9}. The Sn ←N stretching frequencies have been suggested to fall

in the region below 220 cm⁻¹ on coordination^{5,10} and are, therefore, not expected to interfere with the assignment of above bands. The results (Table 1) show that except in case of the complex with morpholine where only one band in the Sn-Cl stretching region appears, there is a multiple splitting in case of the remaining complexes. This suggests a *trans* Cl-Sn-Cl arrangement in morpholine complex, while in all other cases the chlorine atoms appear to occupy *cis* positions¹¹. However, as the splitting of Sn-Cl band could also be due to the solid state effects or the existence of alkyl groups in *trans* as well as in *gauche* forms, the above inferences cannot be regarded as unambiguous ones.

Experimental

Nitrobenzene, diethyl ether and petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) were purified and dried before use by standard methods¹². Morpholine, *o*-toluidine, phenyl hydrazine, piperidine, *N*-ethylpiperidine and triethylamine were purified by keeping them over KOH pellets for a few days and distilled over fresh KOH pellets. Some of the bases were distilled under reduced pressure to avoid decomposition. *p*-Toluidine (B.D.H., A.R.) and *o*-toluidine (Sisco) were used as such.

n-Butyl-*n*-propyltin dichloride was prepared by the reported method⁷. Its complexes with piperidine, morpholine and *N*-ethylpiperidine were prepared by adding dropwise to its solution in petroleum ether, a solution of the base in the same solvent in slight excess with stirring. In case of piperidine the solid complex separated out immediately. For morpholine, the contents were kept at room temperature

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND IMPORTANT IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd	Analysis% Found/(Calcd)			δ_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{Sn-C}}$	$\nu_{\text{Sn-Cl}}$
	Sn	Cl	N			
n-Bu(n-Pr)SnCl ₂ (White, 68-69)	40 58 (41 03)	24 13 (24 47)			600, 545	350, 270-260, 250
n Bu(n-Pr)SnCl ₂ 2PhHy (Pink, 190d)	23 77 (23 50)	14 52 (14 02)	11 61 (11 06)	1 590, 1 600	578, 490	328, 301, 262, 260
n-Bu(n Pr)SnCl ₂ 2 morpholine (White, 158)	25 12 (25 63)	15 43 (15 29)	6 37 (6 03)	1 580, 1 675	580, 525	250
n-Bu(n-Pr)SnCl ₂ TEA (White, Sublime)	30 76 (30 43)	18 24 (18 15)	3 46 (3 58)		600, 539	330, 282
n Bu(n Pr)SnCl ₂ 2 <i>o</i> -toluidine (White, 184d)	23 47 (23 61)	14 70 (14 08)	5 09 (5 55)	1 620, 1 620	560, 510	315, 270
n-Bu(n Pr) SnCl ₂ 2 <i>p</i> toluidine (Dirty yellow, 178d)	23 50 (23 61)	14 41 (14 08)	5 04 (5 55)	1 630, 1 630	480	328, 310
n-Bu(n-Pr) SnCl ₂ 2 <i>o</i> toluidine (Grey, 190d)	16 46 (16 65)	9 40 (9 93)	7 31 (7 83)		600, 550	350, 330
n Bu(n-Pr) SnCl ₂ 2 piperidine (White, 222)	25 76 (25 86)	15 10 (15 43)	6 42 (6 08)	1 590, 1 640	540	262, 225
n-Bu(n Pr) SnCl ₂ 2 NEP (Rust,-) ^a	23 27 (23 04)	13 79 (13 74)	5 31 (5 42)		535	288-80, 265

^aM p could not be determined accurately

for ~5 h to get an appreciable yield. In case of *N*-ethylpiperidine, instead of a solid complex a sticky mass was obtained which after keeping in an ice-bath for ~7 h and on scratching the sides of the container yielded a rust coloured powdered complex. For the preparation of *o*-toluidine complex the solutions of both the Lewis acid and base in dry diethyl ether were mixed and refluxed for ~0.5 h and then left at room temperature overnight. The solution of phenyl hydrazine prepared in dry diethyl ether was added to a solution of Lewis acid in petroleum ether. The complex of *p*-toluidine with n-butyl-n-propyltin dichloride was prepared by mixing their hot solutions in petroleum ether and shaking the mixture for ~4 h to get a dirty yellow coloured solid. A similar procedure was adopted for the preparation of the complex of *o*-toluidine.

All the complexes were washed several times with the solvent and dried by keeping them under reduced pressure for several hours. Their stoichiometries were established on the basis of their tin,

chlorine and nitrogen contents. Ir spectra (nujol) were taken on Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer using sodium chloride and polyethylene windows.

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NOTE

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